

GOAL-ORIENTED TEACHING ENGLISH TO REFUGEES AND IMMIGRANTS

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Abstract: *English is one of international languages and it is impossible not to speak it for immigrants who moved to another country, especially, in the European Union. This presentation focuses on the educational issues connected with teaching English to refugees and immigrants, namely, how to determine their needs, adapt lessons to learners' needs, motivate them for better learning, what aspect of language should be given more emphasis on, i.e. what language structures are the most important to learn? In this presentation we are going to find out basic formula for teaching survival or everyday English to the target group of learners.*

Key words: survival language, alienation, marginalization, refugee, migrant, bilingual, andragogy, lifelong learning, target group.

Introduction

According to Wikipedia "European refugee crisis began in 2015, when a rising number of refugees and migrants made the journey to the European Union to seek asylum, travelling across the Mediterranean Sea or through Southeast Europe".

Eurostat says, "EU member states received over 1.2 million first time asylum applications in 2015, a number more than double that of the previous year".

At the end of 2014 the total number of forcibly placed people reached 60 million, the highest level since World War II.

All this turmoil resulted in a vast population in Europe who do not know the area language and cannot integrate into society. Inability to speak at least English in a foreign country deprives a person of social integration, self-actualisation and job opportunities. Majority of young adults who fled into Europe have a university degree and are quite fluent in English. So, as the target group for learning English in this area mostly fall children and adults. Children from vulnerable groups have English as a compulsory subject at school as their peers, therefore, I will try to investigate adults' goal-oriented learning English. In this presentation they will be referred to as 'learners'.

Goal Oriented Teaching Methodology

"In Goal Oriented Teaching, we can divide goals into Major and Minor. The Major Goal is the acquisition of English as a Second Language. The Minor Goal supports the Major Goal by employing various lessons that have fixed objectives. For example, minor

goals can focus on prepositions, articles, tenses, mood and aspect, and brevity, and other grammatical issues". (Agarwal, C., 2013, 40) The minor goals lead the learners to the major goal. Since the presentation is on adult learning let us define it scientifically. A study about adult learning is called andragogy which originated in 1950s. It is said in the *Handbook for Adult Teaching Staff (2014)*: "Andragogy assumes in adult learning the following: 1) Adults need to know why they need to learn something; 2) Adults need to learn experientially; 3) Adults approach learning as problem-solving; and 4) Adults learn best when the topic is of immediate value." That means that instruction for adults needs to focus more on the process and less on the content being taught. Techniques such as case studies, role-playing, simulations, and self-evaluation are of most help. Educators adopt a role of facilitator or resource rather than lecturer or evaluator (Kolb, 1984).

As an adult who belongs to a vulnerable social group starts a learning programme, s/he may face the following emotions:

- Fear of criticism by the rest of the group
- Anxiety and depression
- Alienation and marginalization
- Negative self-image, low self-esteem, feelings of obsolescence
- Passive or even aggressive attitude
- Discouragement

On the contrary, an adult learner may have positive feelings as well such as hope for the prospects education has to offer, optimism and high self-esteem if the mentor is supportive, has respect for their individuality and believes in their abilities (Athanasios et al, 2014, 27). These internal and external barriers may influence the learners' decision to go on with the programme or leave it. Therefore, teachers as facilitators and mentors should focus their attention not only on educational objectives, but on their learners' psychological state and behavioural patterns as well.

Rogers and Horrocks (2010, 108) claim: "... within any group of adult learners, there will be a wide variety of needs, and within each participant there will be a different mixture of needs. This mixture will be constantly changing as the learning proceeds and as the individual's life situation changes. This is why predetermined and uniform learning outcomes can never be achieved in adult learning programmes. Each adult learner will take away from any learning situation what they require; learning is unique to each learner and uncertain". As a technique to improve English course design for adult refugees and immigrants I suggest educators to conduct needs analysis where there will be illustrated students' needs, background and motivation. This way the content of the course may be adapted to the learner expectations. The English programme being a part of the so-called lifelong learning and learners' personal development will lead to their social inclusion, social integrity and economic and cultural enhancement. (Kokkos, 2011). The term of lifelong learning is defined by European Commission

(2001) as “all learning activity undertaken throughout life, with the aim of improving knowledge, skills and competence, within a personal, civic, social, and/or employment-related perspective” (Planning Bureau, 2007, 2). It is any adult’s undeniable right and cannot be neglected.

As a difference between andragogy and pedagogy Knowles (1980, 44) states that “adults are goal oriented”. Therefore, the course taught to the target group of adults should be purposeful, straight to the point and resourceful. Kokkos states (2005), emphasis should be given to skills that learners can implement to real-life situations and not to abstract concepts, because adults are more problem-centered than content-centered.

1. A Sample Three-month Survival English Course for Targeted Learners

A sample course for teaching basic survival English to adults is supposed to take three months and it is going to help the learners to become a part of the society they are living in: make phone calls, appointments, go shopping, use services, etc.

The lessons will be three times a week with at least one day interval. The purpose of lessons and skills gained will be interchangeable, i.e. if one lesson focuses on grammar, reading and writing, the next one will concentrate on listening and speaking. Here’s an example of one-month learning organization:

Lesson #	Topic	Skills	Tasks	Phrases
1	Introducing yourself	Speaking, Listening	Self-introduction	Let me introduce myself. My name is ...
2	Jobs	Reading, Writing	Reading a sample CV, writing one’s own	I work as a ..., I am looking for a job as a ...
3	Likes, dislikes	Speaking, Listening	Speaking about your likes and dislikes.	I like I don’t like ... I love/ hate ...
4	At the doctor’s	Reading, Speaking, Listening	Reading a dialogue between a patient and a doctor, making their own.	I have a problem in ... I need to see ...
5	Going shopping	Reading, Speaking, Listening	Reading a dialogue between a customer and a salesperson, making their own	How much is ...here can I find... Can you show me ...
6	At the chemist	Speaking,	Listening	I need medicine for ...

		Listening	dialogu and making their own	Do you have any ...
7	Writing emails	Reading, Writing	Reading a sample email and writing their own	Basic structure of informal and formal email
8	Making appointments	Speaking, Listening	Listening to a phone call where a speaking is making an appointment, making their own.	Can we meet on ... Is it possible to meet ... I am free on ...
9	Writing letters	Reading, Writing	Reading a sample formal letter to the landlord and making their own	I am writing you because ... Can we negotiate the matter of ...
10	Buying groceries	Speaking, Listening	Listening to the dialogue and making their own	Can I have some ... I need some ... I cannot find ...
11	Map reading	Reading, Speaking	Looking at ad reading a map, asking and giving directions	How can I get to ... Where is ... Turn/go ...
12	At local school	Speaking, Listening	Listening to the dialogue between a parent and a teacher and making their own	Can we talk about my child's ... Does he/she have any problems in ...

Conclusion

Since adult teaching should be goal-oriented and straightforward, while helping adult immigrants to become an integral part of the society they are living in, the lessons should be organized thoroughly, have a clear objective and a vivid learning outcome, even though each learner takes from the lesson what they need. Nowadays people are encouraged to help refugees by different means such as donations or volunteering. For volunteering as an English trainer special qualifications or skills are not required, just being a language bearer is enough. Thus, anyone who has an

opportunity whether a teacher of English or not can make a difference in this world and help refugees and immigrants to overcome language and social barriers, occupy their own place in the society and, finally, find their home.

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